

ABSTRACTS of the

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In Silico Analysis of Keto Derivatives of Bile Acids as Cardioprotective TGR5 Activators

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Abstract

Background/Aim: TGR5, a metabotropic receptor that is G-protein-coupled to the induction of adenylate cyclase, has been recognized as the molecular link connecting bile acids to the control of energy and glucose homeostasis. Activation of TGR5 has cardioprotective effects against high glucose-induced cardiomyocyte injury and could be a pharmacological target for the treatment of diabetic cardiomyopathy.¹ Natural bile acids are TGR5 ligands, however structural modifications of natural bile acids, such as the replacement of hydroxyl with keto groups, have continuously been made in an attempt to reduce the cytotoxicity without reducing their ability to promote membrane permeability and bind to the receptors.² Recently, the cryo-electron microscopy structures of GPBAR-Gs complexes stabilized by the semisynthetic bile acid derivative INT-777 (6 α -ethyl-23(S)-methylcholic acid) were reported.³ The objectives of the study were to assess the cardioprotective potential of natural and semisynthetic bile acids by analyzing their binding affinity for TGR5.

Methods: The three-dimensional (3D) crystal structure of TGR5 receptor in a complex with INT-777 (PDB code: 7CFN) was retrieved from the Protein Data Bank and the ligand structures were drawn in ChemDraw software and geometrically optimized using Chem3D software. Binding affinities of bile acids to TGR5 receptor were determined by molecular docking analysis using Molegro Virtual Docker software.

Results: While INT-777 as expected had the highest binding affinity towards the active site of TGR5 receptor (-103.13 kcal/mol), the investigated bile acids and their derivatives exerted binding affinities in the range from -94.10 to -99.27 kcal/mol. 3,7,12-triketocholic acid (TKC) and 7,12-diketocholic acid (DKC) had the highest affinities to TGR5 receptor active site, higher than those of natural bile acids cholic acid and deoxycholic acid, while 12-monoketodeoxycholic acid (MKDC) exerted the lowest binding affinity. TKC and DKC have 15 and 10 times higher values of critical micellar concentration in comparison to cholic acid, which makes them good candidates for further investigations since they possess very low cytotoxicity.

Conclusion: Identified semisynthetic bile acids with better pharmacological properties have high potential to succeed in later stages of research in biological systems as potential cardioprotective agents.

Key words: TGR5; Cardioprotection; Bile acids; Molecular docking.

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